

O'ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILLARIDA QO'SHMA OTLARNING QIYOSIY- TIPOLOGIK TADQIQI

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Annotatsiya: mazkur maqolada qo'shma otlarning turli tizimli tillaridagi o'xshash hamda farqli jihatlari, qo'shma otlarning ko'plik shaklini yasashda muayyan qoidalarga bo'ysunishi misollar orqali yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: qo'shma ot, ko'plik, o'zak morfema, struktur-semantik birlik, leksema

Qo'shma otlar ikki yoki undan ortiq o'zak morfemaning qo'shilishidan hosil bo'lgan va yagona struktur-semantik birlikni tashkil etgan so'zlardir. Misol uchun o'zoynak, bilakuzuk, uchburchak, atirgul, bo'tako'z, nomoz- shomgul, mehmondo'st, erksevar kabi.

Qo'shma so'zlar yasalishi uchun asos bo'lgan so'zlar o'zlarining dastlabki ma'nolarini qisman yoki butunlay yo'qotadi: ular birgalikda tamoman yangi lug'aviy ma'no bildiradi. Chunonchi, osh va qozon so'zlari alohida leksemalar sifatida o'z lug'aviy ma'nolariga ega. Lekin ularning qo'shilishidan hosil bo'lgan oshqozon so'zi mazkur so'zlarning dastlabki ma'nolaridan farqlanuvchi yangi ma'noni — "inson va hayvonlarning ovqat hazm qilish a'zo-si" ma'nosini bildiradi. Qo'ziqorin, itog'iz, oqsoch, oqsuyak, kampirchopon singari qo'shma so'zlar haqida ham shunday fikrni aytish mumkin.

Qo'shma so'zlar qismlari orasidagi ma'no munosabati har xil. Ular o'xshatish, qiyoslash (karnaygul, otquloq, tuyaqush, sheryurak, qo'yko'z), xoslik, biror narsaga mo'ljallanganlik (gultuvak, molqo'ra, olovkurak, tokqaychi, qiymataxta), biror o'rin-joyga mansublik (suvilon, tog'olcha, cho'lyalpiz, qo'qonarava), biror belgiga nisbat berish (achchiqtosh, olaqarg'a, sho'rdanak, qizilishton, Qiziltepa), miqdorga munosabat (beshbarmoq, mingoyoq, qirqog'ayni, Beshariq) va boshqa ma'nolarni anglatadi.

Ingliz tilida qo'shma otlarning uch hil yasalish usullari mavjud:

- 1) open or spaced, ya'ni, ajratib yoziladigan otlar, misol uchun, tennis shoe;
- 2) hyphenated, ya'ni, chiziqcha bilan ajratib yoziladigan otlar, misol uchun six-pack;

3) closed or solid ya'ni, qo'shilib yoziladigan otlar, misol uchun, bedroom;

Quyida ingliz tilida qo'shma otlarga misollarni ko'rib chiqsak:

Noun+ noun: bus stop; ot+ot: autobus bekati.

1-misol. Is this the **bus stop** for the number 12 bus?

Adjective+ noun: blackboard, full moon, software; sifat+ot: doska, to'lin oy, dasturiy ta'minot

2-misol. A few weeks ago, there was an extremely big **full moon**, closer to the earth than ever before. (O'zbek tilida: Bir necha hafta oldin Yerga har qachongidan ham yaqinroq bo'lgan juda katta **to'lin oy** paydo bo'ldi.)

Verb(ing)+ noun: washing machine, swimming pool

3-misol. Put the clothes in the red **washing machine**. (O'zbek tilida: Kiyimlarni qizil **kir yuvish mashinasiga** soling.)

Noun + verb: haircut, sunrise, train- spotting

Ot+fe'l: soch turmagi, quyosh chiqishi, poezd-spotling

4-misol. I like to get up at sunrise. (O'zbek tilida: Men **quyosh chiqqanda** turishni yaxshi ko'raman.)

O'zbek tilida qo'shma otlarning ko'pligini yasash uchun -lar qo'shimchasini qo'shish orqali amalga oshirilishi hech qanday muammoga ega emasligini misollarda ko'rib chiqamiz: ko'zoynak(lar), bilaguzuk(lar), uchburchak(lar), atirgul(lar), qo'ziqorin(lar), kungaboqar(lar) lekin ingliz tilida qo'shma otlarning ko'plik qo'shimchasini qo'llash uchun ma'lum qoidalar mavjuddir, ularni quyida misollar orqali ko'rib chiqamiz:

5-misol: a school teacher- **three school teachers**, one assistant headmaster - **five assistant headmasters**, the sergeant major -**some sergeants major**, a mother-in-law- **two mothers-in-law**, an assistant secretary of state- **three assistant secretaries of state**,

my toothbrush- **our toothbrushes**, a woman-doctor -**four women-doctors**, a doctor of philosophy -**two doctors of philosophy**, a passerby/ a passer-by- **two passersby/ two passers-by**.

Xulosa o'rinda shuni aytishimiz joizki, o'zbek va ingliz tilida qo'shma otlarning yasaliş usullarining o'xshash hamda farqli tomonlari mavjud, biroq qo'shma otlarning ko'plik shaklini yasalişini ingliz tilida muayyan qoidalarga bo'ysungan holda amalga oshiriladi

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